

RESEARCH REPORT
October 2023
TREPA Series 14-2023

Reflective Journaling Guide

PREPARED BY:

Natalia Muñoz Cassolis and Meredith L. Gore

TREPA

Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

This publication is one of a series of scholarly products resulting from investigations of human dimensions of global environmental change. The Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals studies risk at the intersection of human-wildlife conflicts and diseases of animals using a team science approach.

A LIST OF TREPA PUBLICATIONS MAY BE OBTAINED BY ACCESSING OUR WEBSITE AT:

www.conservationcriminology.com/trepa/

CITE THIS DOCUMENT:

Muñoz Cassolis, N., and Gore, M.L. **Reflective Journaling Guide**. Threat Reduction for the Environment, People and Animals. Department of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral and Social Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park. College Park, MD. 9 pp.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The project or effort depicted was or is sponsored by the Department of Defense, Defense Threat Reduction Agency. The content of the information does not necessarily reflect the position or the policy of the federal government, and no official endorsement should be inferred.

INTRODUCTION

TREPA's award requires all team members to engage in reflective journaling as a mechanism to evaluate the project's performance. Feedback resulting from this process needs to be reported to the donor on an annual basis via TREPA's annual report, due on **June 30 every year**. In TREPA's case, the reflective journaling process aims to contribute to (i) assessing if all tasks allocated for the specific year were conducted, (ii) describing the resources that were required for their completion, and (iii) identifying any needed adjustments for the overall project.

Reflective journaling is based on the concept of '*reflection-on-action*'. This means the ability to observe and analyze an event that happened in the past, thus requiring to look in hindsight at a particular experience and describe what happened and what can be learned from it. Yet, reflective journaling can also help improve an individual's ability to '*reflect-in-action*', enhancing the ability to analyze a situation as it happens. Thus, reflective journaling is a fundamental tool for recording and collecting lessons learned on an individual basis. We will produce further guidelines on recording and collecting lessons learned as a group. Yet, please bear in mind the importance of reflective journaling for your individual learning process and as a tool to spark conversations later at a group level.

There are multiple methodologies and guidelines on how to do reflective journaling. For TREPA, we have selected Roger Greenaway's **Four Fs for active reviewing model**. TREPA believes this simplified version of the Gibbs Reflective Cycle can make reflective journaling less burdensome while still collecting essential lessons learned and evaluating TREPA's performance. However, TREPA encourages all team members to explore other options if they don't feel comfortable with the Four Fs model and/or find another model more compelling or synergistic with their worldview and lived experiences. There is no right or wrong way of doing reflective journaling, and these guidelines only aim at facilitating the exercise for all team members.

Since a journal is a *'collection of entries made on a regular basis'*¹, we encourage all team members to adopt this practice for TREPA at least once a month. Reflective journaling can be undertaken on paper-based documents, digital formats or by creating your own template on platforms such as [Easy Retro](#). However, by **May 30 every year**, we kindly request all team members to submit a brief summary of TREPA's evaluation resulting from this process to Meredith Gore (gorem@umd.edu) so it can be reported to the donor. **Appendix A** has a template you can use for your yearly summary.

THE FOUR FS FOR ACTIVE REVIEWING

Purpose of the model: have individuals critically examine a situation, collect their impressions, and think about how to use the lessons learned in the future.

The four Fs are:

1. **Facts:** an objective account of what happened
2. **Feelings:** a description of the emotional reactions to the situation
3. **Findings:** the concrete learnings that arise from the situation
4. **Future:** determining how to use the lessons learned in future situations

Stage 1: Facts

At this stage, team members look at what happened and examine the sequence of events and critical moments. It is important for this section to remain as objective as possible; thus, try to avoid including any judgment or opinions. Some of the questions that can guide you in this stage are as follows:

- What, where, who, when?
- What was the timeline of the event/situation?
- What happened right before the event/situation?

¹ https://www.westernsydney.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/1082779/Reflective_writing_Structure.pdf

- What happened immediately after the event/situation?
- What exactly happened? What worked? What didn't work?
- What was expected to happen?
- Did anything unexpected happen? What was the most surprising?
- Did anything very predictable happen?
- What were some of the most interesting/different/memorable discoveries I made while engaging in this activity?
- What were some of the most critical moments?
- What influenced your attitude and behavior the most?
- What didn't happen, although you were expecting it to happen?

Examples

An interviewee was reluctant to participate in a focus group. The interviewee raised concerns on how the data was going to be managed and shared. One team member reached out and explain the data collection protocol in detail. The interviewee was at ease and decided to participate in the activity.

While sampling a carcass one of the rangers refused to wear gloves. A team member explained that there was a protocol in place, and it was important to wear gloves for his own protection. Upon explaining in detail why it is important, the ranger decided to wear the gloves.

Stage 2: Feelings

Please describe how you felt about the situation. In this section, you also should include any thoughts or ideas you had while experiencing the situation. However, try to avoid using emotions as synonyms for judging. For example, try rephrasing *'I felt I made the right calls while others didn't'* into *'I felt confident with the decisions I made'*. Some helpful questions to prompt this section are:

- What are my first thoughts about this situation/event or the overall project?
- How did the situation make you feel?
- What were some of the feelings I experienced?
- What were some of my most challenging moments, and what made them so?

- What were some of my most rewarding moments, and what made them so?
- At what point did you feel most or least involved?
- At what points were you most aware of controlling/expressing your feelings?

Stage 3: Findings

At this stage, team members are encouraged to analyze the situation and try to answer as many questions on 'How?' and 'Why?' as possible. This is where team members are encouraged to find meaning and make assessments. Some guiding questions can be:

- Why did [x, y, and z] not work? Why did [x, y, and z] work?
- How did [x, y, and z] influence the outcome?
- How did I address challenges, and how did it work?
- How did your role have an impact on the situation?
- What needs to change and why?
- What would you like to have done differently / more of / less of?
- What could have been done to have a different outcome?
- Are there any missed opportunities or regrets?
- What did you learn about yourself/the team/ other people/the project?
- How has the research contributed to my understanding of the system/problem?

Stage 4: Future

At this point, team members are encouraged to think about how the findings can reshape future action. Team members should reflect on how previous experiences can change future actions and what needs to be done to achieve those changes. Some prompt questions for these purposes can be:

- What would I suggest to someone willing to engage in a similar activity/event/situation or research project?
- How would you address the situation if you could go back in time?
- How can you plan for the future?
- What choices do you have to address a similar situation in the future?

- How do you imagine using what you learned?
- What changes would you like to see? What changes have already occurred?

Appendix A
Summary Template

Reflective Journaling	
Prepared by:	Add the name of the team member
Period:	09 2023 - 05 2024

Summary

Write a brief description of the situations analyzed and the main lessons learned.

	Facts	Feelings	Findings	Future
Situation 1				
Situation 2				
Situation 3				
Situation 4				
Situation 5				
Situation 6				